

The ARCHI method: a tool for diagnosing tree vitality

B. Snoussi, B. Chapelet, C. Drénou, G. Sajdak

General informations about SPNA operational group

SPNA (Precision forestry in Nouvelle-Aquitaine) is a project funded by the Poitou-Charentes 2014/2020 rural development program - Call for sub-measure 16.1 Operation A “Support for the creation and operation of EIP operational groups” - Action 2 “Funding of operational groups”. SPNA’s initial aim is to develop and disseminate innovative tools recently developed or close to implementation, to facilitate and encourage the sustainable management of Pinus pinaster and Chestnut in Nouvelle Aquitaine, France. This operational group seek to develop and disseminate technical and economic tools to help managers in their silvicultural choices, and to characterize the state and possible evolution of certain regional species in a context of climate change.

The Institute for Forestry Development (IDF), the applied research and development department of the National Center of Forest Ownership (CNPF), was the project coordinator, with local involvement from the CNPF Nouvelle-Aquitaine Delegation. The project involves ten regional forestry partners and stakeholders from Research, R&D, public and private forest management, as well as representatives of forest owners and local authorities: Alliance Forêts Bois, CC Fumel Vallée du Lot, Department of Forest Health (DSF) of the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty (MASA), El Purpan, FCBA, GDF Sud-Dordogne, IGN, INRAE, ONF Centre-Ouest-Aquitaine.

1.Context

Uncertainty surrounds the ability of trees to withstand abrupt climate change. Developed in 2010, the ARCHI method owes its acronym to “architecture”. The aim of the ARCHI method is to offer a visual field diagnostic method for estimating tree resilience. This method has led to the production of ARCHI determination keys.

Chestnut in the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region is the second most important deciduous tree species in terms of area, with over 250,000 ha and a production of 38,400 m³/year, i.e. 35% of the national production. Its decline is of concern to professionals in the sector, and raises the key question of diagnosing the state and health of the trees. Chestnut is the 3rd largest deciduous species in France, accounting for 50% of the world's chestnut woodland.

Training sessions in the ARCHI method, applied to chestnut trees, were held during the SPNA operational group.

2. ARCHI method, a dual diagnosis

The ARCHI method is a visual diagnostic tool for assessing tree decline and resilience. It allows us not to be misled by sometimes temporary symptoms, and not to sentence stressed trees before knowing their natural evolution.

It is based on a reading of aerial architecture.

Ontogenic diagnosis

Each species has a number of axis categories with precise functions that form the species' Architectural Unit (AU). The crown of a young tree becomes rounder, most often as a result of the AU's duplication into master branches, which then duplicate into smaller and smaller branches according to a genetically programmed sequence. Identifying the tree's stage of development is known as ontogenic diagnosis. Four stages can be distinguished (Figure 1): young, adult, mature and senescent.

Figure 1: Example of a development sequence (case of the pedunculate oak, *Quercus robur* L) with details of the crown axes. (Fig. 1.1: Young stage ; Fig. 1.2: Adult stage ; Fig. 1.3: Mature stage ; Fig. 1.4: Senescent stage.
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Physiological diagnosis

Like all living entities, trees experience crises of varying magnitude. From a normal state (healthy tree), under the influence of various factors, there may be deviations from normal (stressed tree) followed by a return to normality (resilient tree). This cyclical behavior is common and contributes to the longevity of trees. On the other hand, if the tree undergoes too much stress, or if this stress lasts too long, or even if it returns too quickly, the situation becomes more complicated. The deviation from normal is so great that a point of no return is reached. The tree is then in a state of irreversible decline, a condition so fragile that all it takes is a few aggravating factors to lead to an inevitable death.

Figure 2: Example of normal branching (Fig. 2.1) and impoverished branching (Fig. 2.2) for oaks (*Quercus robur*, *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*).
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Figure 3 : Presentation of the three types of substitute shoots according to the ARCHI method : Orthotropic (Fig. 3.1), Plagiotropic (Fig. 3.2) and Ageotropic (Fig. 3.3) for oaks (*Quercus robur*, *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*).
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The list for deciduous species is: *Castanea sativa*, *Quercus robur*, *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, *Q. suber*, *Q. ilex*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Platanus x acerifolia*.

The list for the coniferous species is: *Pseudotsuga menziesii*, *Picea abies*, *Pinus pinaster*, *P. sylvestris*, *P. nigra* (ssp. *nigra*, ssp. *laricio* var. *corsicana*, ssp. *salzmannii*), *P. uncinata*, *Abies alba*, *Cedrus atlantica*.

The architectural determination keys integrate three series of observations: sequential structure (or ontogenic diagnosis); symptoms of crown degradation and restoration processes.

Each key guides the observer by asking questions with binary answers, leading to seven possible diagnoses (healthy tree, stressed tree, resilient tree, tree showing crown descent, fallback, tree in irreversible decline, and dead tree) (Figure 5). In addition, these 7 states are combined with the 4 stages of development, giving 16 combinations for *Castanea sativa* and 19 for *Cedrus atlantica*.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of the ARCHI method and associated typologies.

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This tool is primarily intended for the various technical stakeholders (managers, technical personnel, arboriculturists, etc.), to provide them with advice on stand management and monitoring. It also has obvious educational value for teachers. ARCHI can be applied in fields as varied as biology, silviculture, autoecology and genetics.

4. Conclusions

The ARCHI method enables to decipher a tree's past and present dynamics, and to predict its evolution, at least in the short term. It provides a diagnosis of whether a decline is reversible (resilience) or irreversible. It helps to avoid being misled by sometimes temporary symptoms, such as leaf deficit or branch mortality, and to differentiate natural mortality linked to ageing from decline. It explains the non-linear dynamics of tree response to stress, incorporates the botanical specificities of each species and takes into account the observation of substitute shoots. Finally, it sets out a hierarchy of observations to be carried out in the form of determination keys.

It requires a learning phase to establish an ARCHI diagnosis with precision. Observations are even more difficult to complete in dense, tall forests. Observation difficulties are not unique to ARCHI. They are linked to tree height, density, slopes, etc. All visual methods are confronted with them.

For fir, the presence of mistletoe can mask a large part of the architecture, thus rendering the method unusable. The ARCHI method does not characterize a tree's health status, but rather reflects its ability to overcome a situation or succession of stresses. This method does not identify the causes of decline, nor does it explain differences in behavior within the same stand. Finally, ARCHI diagnosis can only be carried out on dominant and co-dominant trees, as it cannot take into account the competition factor.

The Institute for Forestry Development (IDF) is coordinating the SPNA-Diff project, financed by the European Union (FEADER) and the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region, which aims to transfer knowledge and skills around new skills and technologies, many of which emerged from the SPNA operational group.

Further information

Find out more about the ARCHI method on the National Center of Forest Ownership's dedicated page:

<https://www.cnpf.fr/nos-actions-nos-outils/outils-et-techniques/archi>.

The English translation of an article published in the scientific and technical journal Forêt & Innovation n°12 (The ARCHI method, a key to understanding trees, Christophe Drénou, 2025) :

https://www.cnpf.fr/sites/socle/files/2025-03/Article%20Archi%20EN_FI12_2025.pdf.

Find out more about the SPNA operational group on the National Center of Forest Ownership's (Nouvelle-Aquitaine Delegation) dedicated page:

<https://nouvelle-aquitaine.cnpf.fr/nos-actions/reseaux-d-experimentations-et-d-etudes/le-changement-climatique>.

Find out more about the SPNA-Diff project on the National Center of Forest Ownership's dedicated page:

<https://www.cnpf.fr/actualites/projet-spna-diff-les-videos-et-fiches-techniques-sont-disponibles>.

Contacts

Benjamin Chapelet, benjamin.chapelet@cnpf.fr

Bilal Snoussi, bilal.snoussi@cnpf.fr

Matevž Triplat, matevz.triplat@gozdis.si

FOREST4EU partners:

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 info@forest4eu.eu

